

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-42-IBN-5-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	3	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	4 42
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	248.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 248.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/8/2022 19:18:28 CST		
Date Processed:	6/22/2023 22:22:12 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.597	17124640	49.75	2006317
2	6.952	17296775	50.25	1888729

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-41-IBN-5-5% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	91	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	2	Processing Method:	LRM 4 41
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	248.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 248.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 8:14:55 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 8:31:28 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.630	374849	3.32	46312
2	6.957	10923328	96.68	1234864